

INNODIVERSITY IN THE SPANISH BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT 2019

SYNOPSIS

Celia de Anca and
Salvador Aragón

Authors

What is the Innodiversity Index?

“Innodiversity is the organizational capacity to jointly manage diversity and innovation and improve competitiveness”

Celia de Anca, Salvador Aragón

What is the Innodiversity Index?

The Innodiversity Index is an analysis and diagnosis tool to quantify how companies manage innodiversity as part of their strategy in search of greater competitiveness.

The relevance of innodiversity management is justified by three basic premises demonstrated by the research:

This **innovative index**, created by researchers Celia de Anca and Salvador Aragón, has been put into practice in the Spanish business environment thanks to the framework provided by the **Diversity Lab, the IE Foundation and the Foundation for Diversity, with support from the Pfizer and HP companies and the collaboration of AmChamSpain.**

The Innodiversity Index was developed using a research tool called the **Tree of Innodiversity**. This tool allows companies to **compare their diversity management, innovation management and innodiversity management with the best practices developed by the most advanced companies in each field globally.** Based on this comparison, participating companies can discover their degree of maturity based on four categories:

BENCHMARK company	Benchmark companies are those which develop policies and actions, measure these to a significant degree, and are beginning to be recognized as a benchmark by other companies.
EXPERT company	Expert companies are those that have launched policies and actions along with corresponding measurement mechanisms.
COMMITTED company	Committed companies have begun to implement policies and actions but without significantly addressing their measurement.
NONCOMMITTED company	Companies that do not have innodiversity or its various components on their agenda.

What are the overall results of the Innodiversity Index?

What are the overall results of the Innodiversity Index?

The results provided by the Innodiversity Index indicate that:

In diversity management, companies attain the rank of **Committed**, which means that they have begun to develop actions linked to diversity management but these actions are still limited and pending subsequent measurement.

Some notable examples:

Large company
"BENCHMARK"

Female
talent

The large company **attains the rank of Benchmark** in its management of female talent.

Experiential
diversity

Small and medium-sized
"EXPERTS"

Small and medium-sized companies **attain the rank of Expert** in their management of experiential diversity.

Companies in the sample
"COMMITTED"

Cognitive
diversity

The companies in the sample **attain the rank of Committed** in their management of cognitive diversity, which is the least developed category of diversity.

THE NONMULTINATIONAL COMPANY
"EXPERT IN
INNOVATION"

The nonmultinational company attains the **rank of Expert in its management of innovation**, but it is the large company which acts as a Benchmark for the rest of companies.

The relationship between diversity management and innovation management attains the rank of **Committed**, as its attention to the joint management of diversity and innovation is still small and just starting out. In this alignment, it is the small company implementing joint management actions and policies with their corresponding measurement mechanisms that stands out.

The most relevant data on the management of Diversity

The most relevant data on the management of Diversity

Demographic Diversity

Experiential Diversity

Cognitive Diversity

DEMOGRAPHIC DIVERSITY

FEMALE TALENT

More than 87% of participating companies include managing **gender diversity** in their strategies. Large companies lead in attention to female talent: 90%. Of professional services companies, 94% pay attention to gender diversity. Compare this to the energy and water sectors, which pay the least attention: only 71% of companies.

DISABILITY

The **talent of people with disabilities** is the second area that attracts the most interest, with 72% of companies responding in the affirmative. At 79%, the technology and telecommunications sector leads the talent management of people with disabilities.

SENIORS

Of all companies, 66% claim to pay attention to the diversity of **senior talent**. Small companies pay the most attention to senior talent, with 78% responding yes.

LGBTI

There is less interest in **LGBTI talent**: more than 58% of the participating companies declare that they do not pay particular attention to the management of this group. The companies that pay the most attention to this group are those in the consumer services sector, with 60%. Small companies lead in the management of LGBTI talent, with a presence of over 52%.

Diversity in training

Energy Water

Of the companies in the sample, 61% declare that they are interested in **training diversity**, and this is especially so in the energy and water sector (86%).

Experience in the company itself

Consumer goods

Experience in that very company is important to 66% of the companies in the sample, and this is especially true in large companies (70%), local multinationals (70%), and the consumer goods sector (80%).

Diversity in the sector

Energy Water

Of the companies in the sample, 68% claim to manage **experiential diversity** in the sector. In this area, the highlights are large companies with 71%, the local multinationals with 75%, and the energy and water sector with 86%.

Cultural diversity

Financial

There is less interest in the category of **cultural diversity**, with only 43.1% of companies claiming to pay any attention to it. The greatest presence occurs in financial and professional services, which lead with 52%.

Problem solving

Water

Of the companies in the sample, 30% indicate an interest in **managing diversity** in problem solving. Local multinationals lead with 44%, and the energy and water sector stands out with 57%.

Diversity of personalities

Of the companies in the sample, 34.7% pay attention to **diversity of personalities**.

Leadership diversity

Energy Water

Leadership diversity is the one with the largest percentage of positive responses, reaching 41.8%. Large companies lead with 53%, local multinationals with 58%, and the energy and water sector stands out with 86%.

Critical thinking

Financial

Little attention is paid to the diversity of **critical thinking**, with only 22% of companies performing some type of test for it. In this case, the financial services sector stands out above the others (41%).

The most relevant data on the management of Innovation

The most relevant data on the management of Innovation

Of the companies in the sample, 63% manage product/service innovation.

The creation of specific teams and the use of new technologies together constitute the pillars that support the management of product or service innovation, with around 90% of companies being committed to this type of innovation.

Large companies count almost unanimously on the use of new technologies, a key ingredient in their management of product and service innovation, with a usage exceeding 96%

Of large companies that innovate in products or services, 88% measure the number of new products or services introduced in the market, and 85% of them quantify their contribution to sales.

It is very clear that the ability to be perceived as a benchmark company in product or service innovation is much greater in large companies.

The healthcare sector stands out for its highly specialized innovation model based on product/service with over 73% of companies.

This specialization translates into a high degree of measurement of activities in all its dimensions (43%), and a remarkable ability to transform actions and measurements into a clear perception as a benchmark (41%).

Of the companies in the sample, 61% manage process innovation.

The creation of specific teams and the use of new technologies together constitute the pillars that support the management of process innovation, with around 85% of companies being committed to this type of innovation.

The use of new technologies applied to process innovation is in the majority in large companies, in excess of 91%. Large companies are the most committed to measuring innovation, with values exceeding 81%.

Of the companies in the sample, 58% innovate in their business models.

Formal committees are the most widely used mechanism for managing business model innovation, present in over 80% of companies.

Small companies place special value on the use of new technologies, with usage reaching 91%.

Benchmark rankings in business model innovation are clearly occupied by large companies. The generation of disruptive business models is especially noteworthy in large companies, with 44% of them undertaking it.

The most relevant data on the management of **Innodiversity**

The existence of a dialogue between innovation and diversity is acknowledged by 31 % of companies.

WHICH COMPANIES LEAD IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNODIVERSITY?

By SIZE

Large company

Large companies lead the development of innodiversity, with a presence of around 34%. This group is followed by small companies, with 30%, and medium-sized companies, with 26%.

WHICH IS THE MOST USED MEASUREMENT IN THE MANAGEMENT OF INNODIVERSITY?

Interaction between those responsible for innovation and diversity management

Interaction within the company between those responsible for managing innovation, on the one hand, and diversity, on the other, is the most widely used organizational measure in the management of innodiversity, with average values exceeding 90%.

Multinationals of Spanish origin

leads in the commitment to innodiversity. Of such companies, 44% acknowledge implementing innodiversity management measures with the establishment of a dialogue in both areas, compared to 29% of multinationals of foreign origin and 27% of nonmultinational companies.

By REACH

WHO USES THE MEASUREMENT MECHANISMS BEST?

65%

SMALL COMPANY

Small companies makes the best use of the measurement mechanisms for the management of innodiversity, with around 65%.

By SECTOR

The energy and water sector

leads with 57% of companies developing innodiversity. At the opposite extreme are the producers of consumer goods, where only 10% of companies have started on the road to innodiversity. In the rest of the sectors we find the healthcare sector with 27%, consumer or financial services with 31%, or professional services with 34%.

Methodology and sample

The research tool used was the **Tree of Innodiversity**:

<https://www.innodiversidad.es/#/main>

A digital self-diagnosis tool which, as of the date of this report, had been completed by 297 companies, which we can subdivide into:

Listed on the Stock Exchange

64 listed vs. 233 not listed.

By size

By scope of activity

By sector

No. of companies

Consumer services	84
Professional and legal services	50
Industrial and construction	35
Technology and telecommunications	34
Healthcare	21
Consumer goods	10
Energy and water	7
Others	48

To consult the **REPORT ONLINE** please go to:

<https://centerfordiversity.ie.edu>

or

<http://fundaciondiversidad.org>

INNODIVERSITY IN THE SPANISH BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT 2019

SYNOPSIS